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TORCH, a novel time-of-flight detector for LHCb Upgrade-II

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Abstract

The Time Of internally Reflected Cherenkov (TORCH) detector is a proposed large-area time-of-flight detector, designed to enhance the particle identification performance of the LHCb Upgrade-II experiment in the 2–15 GeV/ c momentum range. The full TORCH detector comprises 18 modules. A module consists of a 10 mm thick quartz plate of dimensions $2.5 \times 0.66 \text{ m}^2$ from which the positions and arrival times of Cherenkov photons from a charged track are detected by highly segmented MCP-PMTs. Each MCP-PMT has an active area of $53 \times 53 \text{ mm}^2$ and a granularity of 64×8 pixels, and was developed in collaboration with an industrial partner (Photek). A general overview of TORCH and its operating principles will be reviewed along with recent results from a half-length 1.25 m TORCH prototype module tested at the CERN proton synchrotron. In the most recent beam test in November 2022, the prototype module was instrumented with six MCP-PMTs compared to two MCP-PMTs in previous tests. The status of the analysis of the latest data will be presented.

1 Introduction

The physics programme of the LHCb experiment critically depends on precision tracking and excellent particle identification (PID). In the existing detector, charged hadron PID is provided by two Ring Imaging Cherenkov (RICH) detectors using two gases to cover a wide momentum range, up to $100 \text{ GeV}/c$. The RICH detectors in LHCb have a momentum threshold for light emission of 10 (15) GeV/c for kaons (protons) [1]. Whilst below the kaon threshold it is possible to separate pions from heavier hadrons by the absence of light, here the RICH cannot positively identify kaons. As an example, in multibody decays one of the daughter particles often has a low momentum and adding PID capabilities for such particles improves significantly the experiment's potential. Improvement is especially relevant in the case of Dalitz-plot or amplitude analyses where additional PID capabilities make the efficiency more uniform across the phase-space of decay. The TORCH detector [2] is designed to provide PID identification over the momentum range 2 – $15 \text{ GeV}/c$, with minimal space requirements and low additional material budget.

The proposed detector for the LHCb Upgrade-II comprises 18 modules covering an area of about $6 \times 5 \text{ m}^2$. Each module consists of a quartz radiator of size $250 \times 66 \times 1 \text{ cm}^3$. When a charged particle passes through the radiator, it emits Cherenkov light. The light is propagated via total internal reflection to the end of the radiator, where a focusing block is attached with a cylindrical mirrored surface. The photons themselves will be detected by an array of 11 micro-channel plate photomultipliers (MCP-PMTs) where their position and arrival time is measured. The MCP-PMTs have an active area of $53 \times 53 \text{ mm}^2$ in a $60 \times 60 \text{ mm}^2$ housing. Over the 10 m flight path of TORCH, the time-of-flight difference between kaons and pions with momentum of $10 \text{ GeV}/c$ is about 35 ps and so effective PID requires per-track time resolution of the order 10 – 15 ps . With the designed module, about 20 – 30 photons are detected per particle, which translates to the requirement for a single-photon time resolution of about 70 ps .

Several beam-test campaigns were performed to demonstrate that requirements can be met. In the following we briefly discuss the prototype detector and the necessary infrastructure, the final results from the 2018 beam tests and a preliminary look at the latest campaign in 2022.

2 Test-beam setup

The beam tests were performed using a half height (1.25 m) module. The tests utilise the T9 beamline at CERN's proton synchrotron, which provides pions and protons in the relevant momentum range. In the test-beam run in 2018, the module was equipped with two MCP-PMTs while in 2022, six MCP-PMTs were installed and fully equipped with electronics. The MCP-PMTs were developed in industrial partnership with Photech Ltd. [3]. The readout is based on the NINO [4] and HPTDC chip-sets [5], giving time-stamps of signals using time-over-threshold [6].

Several additional detectors are used to define the beam location and start time, and to provide a trigger. The trigger is based on small scintillators located upstream and a short distance downstream of the TORCH prototype. Timing fingers equipped with single-channel MCP-PMTs provide a time reference. Two threshold RICH detectors are used to separate pions and protons in the beam. The instrumentation is complemented by a EUDET/AIDA beam telescope [7]. The AIDA Trigger Logic Unit (TLU) [8] is used to provide the trigger signal and clock to both beam telescope and TORCH electronics.

In 2018 the TORCH electronics configuration and DAQ software was based on

Labview running on a single PC. During 2022, in order to cope with the larger data rate with more MCP-PMTs, a new DAQ system based on the EUDAQ system has been used.

3 Results of the 2018 beam test

The main goal of the beam tests was to demonstrate that the required per-photon time resolution can be achieved and to verify the detected photon yield. Data were taken with a mixed beam of pions and protons with a momentum of 5 GeV/c, entering the radiator at several positions. This allowed a study of the time resolution as a function of photon propagation time through the radiator as well as number of photon hits. The observed single-photon time resolution comprises several contributions and can be written as

$$\sigma_{\text{TORCH}}^2 = \sigma_{\text{MCP}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{prop}}^2(t) + \sigma_{\text{RO}}^2(N_{\text{pixels}}),$$

where σ_{MCP} is the intrinsic resolution of the MCP-PMT, $\sigma_{\text{prop}}(t)$ is the resolution on the propagation due to chromatic dispersion and the finite pixel size and is assumed to be linear with photon propagation time, and $\sigma_{\text{RO}}^2(N_{\text{pixels}})$ is associated with the readout and photon clustering procedure which inversely scales with the number of localised hit pixels which make up the photon cluster. Table 1 compares the measured values for individual contributions to the expected values needed to achieve the required single-photon resolution. The measured value of σ_{MCP} is already in agreement with the target. The other contributions are generally affected by the electronics calibrations which are expected to improve in future tests due to the development of a dedicated laboratory-based calibration system.

Figure 1 shows the single-photon time resolution as a function of number of photon reflections in the radiator. As expected, with more reflections, the resolution degrades as more reflections correspond to longer photon path lengths. The number of observed photons was also studied. From comparison with simulation, there is a general agreement of the photon yield between data and expectation, with a small discrepancy in the number of events with no photons detected. The full details of the analysis with all relevant results are available in Ref. [9].

4 A first look at 2022 test-beam data

The latest beam test in 2022 was performed with six MCP-PMTs instrumenting just over half the module. Besides verifying the time resolution and photon yield with the larger area covered, the main aim is to demonstrate the TORCH capability to separate pions from protons. To this aim, data were taken at several beam momenta between 3 and 10 GeV/c at a variety of beam entry positions over the

Figure 1: Measured single photon time resolution as a function of number of photon reflections.

	Measurement [ps]		Target [ps]
	Pions	Protons	
$\sigma_{\text{prop}} \times 10^3/t_p$	8.3 ± 0.7	7.6 ± 0.5	3.75 ± 0.8
σ_{MCP}	34.5 ± 8.6	31.0 ± 7.6	33
$\sigma_{\text{RO}} \times \sqrt{N_{\text{Hits}}}$	96.2 ± 6.7	95.0 ± 6.0	60

Table 1: Contributions to the single-photon time resolution measured in the 2018 beam test along with the target expectations to achieve a single-photon time resolution of 70 ps.

Figure 2: Cluster distribution observed across six MCP-MPTs in the 2022 beam test for two different beam entry positions with clear patterns of Cherenkov light.

plate. As a result of the new DAQ and much improved reconstruction software for the beam telescope, it was possible to fully synchronise information on the trigger, reconstructed tracks and TORCH data for the first time. While in the previous beam tests the beam telescope was used to obtain only the average beam spot and beam profile, with the latest data the per-event entry position in the radiator can be determined, which is important for the PID reconstruction.

Examples of cluster maps for two different beam entry positions are shown in Fig. 2. The band pattern is the expected TORCH image and is consistent with expectations from simulation. Effort is ongoing to fully calibrate the electronics boards for time walk of the NINO and integral nonlinearities of the HPTDC. The dedicated calibration system should allow significant improvements in the measurements of photon spatial position and time resolution for both the 2018 and 2022 data-sets.

5 Outlook

The beam tests are well on track to fully demonstrate the TORCH potential as a PID detector for the LHCb Upgrade-II experiment. In the beam tests performed during 2018 it was possible to demonstrate that a single-photon time resolution close to requirements can be achieved and it has been shown that there is a good understanding of the observed photon yield. Data from the latest beam tests in 2022 will enable improvements in the single-photon time resolution as well as demonstrating particle identification. Currently, procurement of the next generation of MCP-PMT and an additional quartz radiator plane is ongoing, providing future possibilities to test a full-size module.

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